

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF STRESS ON HUMAN REACTIONS AND MANAGEMENT PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract

The rapid development of the modern world and the expansion of the information environment increase the daily psychological burden of people, bringing the relevance of stress to the fore. Stress, as an individual's adaptive response to internal and external influences, shows various manifestations in the physical, emotional and behavioral spheres. People's reaction to stress is related to individual characteristics, perception and assessment abilities. Hans Selye explained stress within the framework of the "general adaptation syndrome" and emphasized both positive and negative aspects of stress. Positive stress plays a stimulating role for individual development and motivation, while negative stress can cause physical, emotional and behavioral problems.

Among the causes of stress, uncontrollable situations, internal and external pressures, tension and changes in relationships occupy a special place. Physical manifestations of stress include headache, fatigue, sleep disturbances, high blood pressure and muscle tension, while psychological manifestations include tension, fear, anxiety, indecisiveness and distraction. Stress coping strategies are presented in two main groups: problem-oriented and emotion-oriented approaches. Problem-oriented approaches focus on eliminating the causes of stress, while emotion-oriented approaches serve to regulate the emotional state of the individual.

Physical activity, relaxation techniques, proper breathing, and effective time management play an important role in stress management. Using social support and creating a balance in lifestyle, as well as taking into account the personality characteristics of the individual, are considered key factors in effectively dealing with stress. The article examines the impact of stress on human reactions, ways to cope with stress, and management perspectives, and provides practical recommendations for improving the quality of life of individuals.

Keywords: stress, reaction, general adaptation syndrome, emotional tension, management, psychological well-being

Introduction

Today's rapidly changing living conditions directly affect a person's psychological balance and make the concept of stress an integral part of daily reality. Increasing social demands, accelerating information flow, and the individual's management of various social roles act as the main factors creating psychological tension.

Stress has always existed in human life, but has become a more widely studied topic in recent years due to globalization and the increasing demands of the modern era. Modern scientific approaches evaluate stress as an adaptive response of the human body to external and internal influences from the environment and explain it as a multifaceted psychological process related to physical, emotional and social factors.

"Stress is an English word that refers to the tension and distress that occurs in a person's mental state. In other words, stress is the mental tension caused by difficult and complex factors that a person encounters in his daily activities and in special circumstances. Stress occurs when the body is exposed to unexpected, sudden, unusual extreme effects and has various manifestations" [2, p.168].

"Selye, who continuously conducted research in the field of stress, defined stress in the 1950s as "a stimulus that causes harm to the organism," and later considered it as "a response in the organism resulting from tension." In 1956, he focused on "non-specific general adaptation symptoms" and suggested that stress is "the organism's demonstration of disease symptoms in the face of harmful factors" [3, p.17].

Hans Selye called stress a "general adaptation syndrome." "Selye considers adaptation to be a fundamental characteristic of life. He shows that there are two ways of living: 1) the active way of struggle, 2) the passive way, of avoiding difficulties, of enduring, of being patient" [6, p.6].

"According to Selye, it has 3 phases: 1) general danger and warning phase - alarm phase; 2) resistance phase; 3) shock phase" [4, p.6].

"Hans Selye also called stress a non-specific defense reaction against any extraordinary impact" [5, p.346].

Stress can positively or negatively affect not only physical and psychological health, but also individuals' daily attitudes and behaviors. Stress should not always be considered a negative factor for the organism. While stressful conditions can hinder an individual's capacity, they can also enable them to realize their potential. Mild levels of stress can be stimulating, motivating, and even prompt action. However, as mentioned above, as the level of stress increases, psychological, physical, and behavioral problems can arise for the individual.

Hans Selye used the concept of stress to encompass both good stress (eustress) and bad stress (distress). According to Selye (1974), an optimal level of stress is necessary for the organism to behave, work, and develop. In other words, beneficial stress is a motivation consisting of the sum of psychological and physical strengths required to overcome obstacles and solve problems. Stress, whether positive or negative, can be observed at every stage of an organism's life. Stress is necessary for personal development and satisfaction.

Stress is a state of difficulty or distress felt as a result of everyday events or pressures in interpersonal relationships. It is defined as an emotional, physical, or cognitive response to environmental pressures, conflicts, tensions, and similar stimuli. The same stressor may not elicit the same emotional responses in everyone. How a stressor is perceived by an individual is crucial. The level of stress experienced by a person can vary depending on how they perceive the stressor. For example, the level of stress experienced by everyone will differ in response to events such as the increasing arms race worldwide, wars, marriage, divorce, taking exams, and running a red light. This is because individuals have different perceptions, thought patterns, interpretations, and belief systems regarding these stressors.

Stress is a state of excessive arousal in both mental and physical dimensions, resulting from an individual's perception of internal and external environmental factors as harmful or threatening. When discussing a stressful situation, it's crucial to focus not so much on the situation itself, but rather on how the individual perceives and interprets it, the defense mechanisms they employ, and their coping skills. A stress response can arise when there's an imbalance between the expectations of the environment and the individual's capabilities. Initially, the individual reacts aggressively to the stress, resisting it, and eventually, the stress can escalate to severe levels, culminating in burnout. The causes of stress include: controllability, pushing boundaries, predictability, pressure, frustration, internal conflict, threat, and change. Stress is a manifestation of adaptation that arises from an action, event, or external factor that creates physical and mental expectations in an individual, varying according to psychological state and individual differences. The stress response is a condition created by the straining and threat to the organism's psychological and physical limits. Stress arises not from what is happening in the environment, but from how the organism reacts to the situation.

Stress can be used interchangeably with concepts such as tension, anxiety, conflict, arousal, severe external conditions, emotional distress, threat to self or security, frustration, etc. Individuals experiencing stress may exhibit physical symptoms such as headaches, digestive problems, high blood pressure, difficulty breathing, and excessive sweating, as well as psychological and behavioral symptoms such as anxiety, anger, tension, unhappiness, irritability, difficulty concentrating, pessimism, indecisiveness, sleep disturbances, and irregular eating habits. A number of symptoms occur before or after the onset of stress. In the literature, stress symptoms are classified in different ways. While some studies group stress symptoms under three main headings—physical, psychological, and behavioral—most studies examine them under the headings of physiological and psychological symptoms. This study also prefers this dual classification.

Physiological symptoms. Physical changes in the human body can sometimes be a result of stress. These changes may also be a symptom of a biological problem not caused by stress, but are generally a reaction of the human body to a stressful event. Common physiological symptoms during stress include: loss of appetite

or overeating, weight loss and weakness, chronic fatigue and weakness, insomnia, excessive or irregular sleep, exhaustion, frequent headaches, pain in various parts of the body and joints, shortness of breath, high blood pressure, palpitations, hypersensitivity, emotional changes, tearing, excessive physical pain and suffering, loss of energy, sweating, trembling, allergies, nausea or stomach cramps, hypersensitivity to loud noises, hot or cold flashes.

Psychological symptoms. Psychological symptoms, while not as easily understood as physiological symptoms, are generally quite difficult to notice visually. These symptoms are mostly related to the thought process, the individual's thoughts, and how stress affects this process. Psychological symptoms of stress manifest themselves through the individual's expression of their thoughts to others and their behavior. Common psychological symptoms in stressful situations include: fear and anxiety, excessive nervousness, sensitivity, tension, irritability, incompatibility, feelings of inadequacy, experiencing unwarranted panic, believing everything is meaningless, lack of enjoyment in life, fear of illness or believing one is ill, forgetting tasks, inability to remember events and people, inability to focus on a task for a long time, decreased self-esteem, difficulty making decisions, inability to initiate tasks, generally being pessimistic, anxious, depressed, and focusing on negativity.

Stress management is a very general concept. This general concept is examined in two categories: "direct actions" and "mitigating actions." Direct actions are those aimed at turning negative situations, such as threats and conflicts arising from interaction with the environment, to one's advantage. Examples of direct actions include preparing for danger, exhibiting aggressive behavior, fleeing, or choosing inaction. Mitigating actions, on the other hand, are aimed at relaxing the individual. Through mitigating actions, a person can feel better in emotionally distressing situations and perform their functions more effectively or comfortably.

The essential elements in stress management are: involvement, initiative, willpower, knowledge, and common sense.

A person's coping mechanisms in stressful situations can be divided into two groups: "active and problem-oriented" and "passive and defensive". These methods are considered "adequate" or "functional" if they can reduce or even eliminate stress. Conversely, if they cause more stress, they are called "inadequate" or "dysfunctional" mechanisms. Inadequate methods can also be grouped into two categories:

- ✓ Inappropriate behaviors include: resorting to alcohol and substances, avoidance behaviors, aggression, withdrawal, depression, suicidal tendencies, and other mental health problems.

- ✓ Behaviors aimed at self-deception: various defense mechanisms such as rationalization, repression, denial, and projection.

The adequate methods can be examined in three groups:

✓ Methods focused on the body: various relaxation techniques such as deep muscle relaxation, meditation, and yoga, breathing exercises, proper nutrition, and aerobic gymnastics.

✓ Methods for dealing with emotions and thoughts: making it a habit to approach life like a scientist. Interpreting stressors as opportunities to test abilities rather than threats, learning to test irrational beliefs, being able to share emotions with others, and expressing emotions openly and appropriately.

✓ Situation-specific approaches: improving communication skills, managing time effectively, leveraging social support, developing assertive behaviors, and improving problem-solving skills.

There are two main coping mechanisms that individuals use when faced with stressful or difficult situations: problem-focused and emotion-focused. "Problem-focused coping" involves the individual identifying the stressful situation and taking effective steps to overcome it. "Emotion-focused coping", on the other hand, involves the individual turning to others and seeking social support. This type of coping strategy includes ignoring the existing situation and avoiding any interaction aimed at resolving the problem.

The stress response is not something that needs to be completely blocked or eliminated. To a certain extent, stress is a mental, physical, and emotional response that increases a person's drive and resilience, makes it easier to cope with difficulties, and provides resistance. Most individuals have achieved success through a drive fueled by stress in their lives. This is because stress, when at the appropriate level and quality, is a stimulus that develops, motivates, strengthens, and provides experience to the individual. It is suggested that there are three main goals in coping with stress. These goals can be expressed as follows:

- In the short term: learning all the methods and rules to follow in order to effectively cope with stress.
- In the medium term: to create a lifestyle that minimizes the negative effects of stress by learning about its causes and symptoms, and recognizing its potential impact in advance. To be able to utilize the positive aspects of stress where appropriate.
- In the long term: being able to live a peaceful, healthy, organized, and productive life where stress is managed.

The following are individual strategies that should be used effectively to cope with stress:

Changing personality traits, taking control of life, incorporating humor and jokes into daily life, avoiding comparisons with others, utilizing the advantages and positive aspects of stress and stress responses, and learning to live with chronic and intractable stress.

"The best proven tools for preventing stress are: the ability to properly plan your time (for example, preparing a schedule of priority issues, analyzing the time spent on various types of activities, using time rationally, finding additional time resources); engaging in sports and physical activities; mastering exercise skills, self-hypnosis techniques, and other relaxation methods" [1, p.122].

One of the factors that makes it difficult to cope with stress is personality traits. People who are overly

sensitive, selfish, rigid, anxious, pessimistic, introverted, reactive, aggressive, anxious, ambitious, quick-tempered, and have a predominance of hostile feelings have a very difficult time coping with stress.

Conclusion

Whether stress benefits or harms the individual largely depends on the individual. The stress response can be a burden that threatens a person psychologically and physiologically, but it can also be a source of energy, helping them cope with life's difficulties. When an individual experiences stress, the body automatically reacts: heart rate increases, sweating intensifies, breathing quickens, and muscle tension increases. In short, the body goes into a state of alert. It is possible to cope with this state of alertness, that is, with stress. A large part of the stress an individual experiences is not in the event or situation itself, but in the meaning they attach to it. Stress management requires awareness of the changes in the body and mind. Furthermore, avoiding or minimizing the use of thought patterns that lead to stress will be beneficial. Proper breathing can send a message to the body that everything is alright. In addition, one of the most important methods of coping with stress is regular exercise. Because regular exercise relaxes muscles, regulates breathing, and helps with healthier thinking and feeling. Leading a passive and inactive life reinforces stress. Another point to consider is regular and sufficient sleep and healthy eating. Lack of sleep or irregular sleep and unhealthy eating can create a vicious cycle, feeding off each other and causing more stress. Effective time management is also an effective method for coping with stress. Time management generally consists of three steps: planning, implementation, and evaluation. Another stress management technique is eliminating uncertainty. Uncertainty is one of the most significant sources of stress. Reducing uncertainties in life and controlling the controllable aspects will reduce stress.

In summary, the following points are recommended for stress management:

Being able to say "no," not being overly perfectionistic, sharing, not hoarding, having hoarding habits, making time for yourself, prioritizing sports and healthy eating, taking good care of your body, learning breathing exercises and relaxation techniques, spending time with loved ones, not neglecting rest, being organized, and not procrastinating.

For this reason, recognizing stress, properly assessing it, and developing management skills is considered one of the key conditions for maintaining an individual's psychological well-being and improving their quality of life.

References

1. Akhundova N.F. Organizational behavior. "University of Economics" Publishing House. Baku, 2014
2. Bayramov A.S. Alizade A.E. Psychology. "CHINAR-CHAP" Publishing and Printing Enterprise. Baku, 2009

3. Gokgoz H. The effect of stress on employee performance: a study on teaching staff. Graduate thesis. Edirne, 2013
4. Seyidov S.I., Hamzayev M.A. Psychology. Baku, 2007
5. Shamilov B.E. (translator) Selye Hans. Stress. General adaptation syndrome. Baku, 2009
6. Shamilov B.E. Stress... Relativism... Psychoanalysis. Baku, 2007